

Studies on Hydroxamic Acids: Part II. N-Aryl Hydroxamic Acids as Reagents for Vanadium (V)

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An investigation of the coloured complexes of 27 N-aryl hydroxamic acids with vanadium(V) in concentrated hydrochloric acid media has been made. The absorption spectra of the chloroform extracts of these complexes have been determined. The effects of attaching various substituent groups to the carbon and nitrogen atoms of the hydroxamic acid functional grouping, which are prominently reflected in the spectral characteristics of the corresponding vanadium(V) complexes, have been discussed. As a result of the present and previous studies, certain concepts have developed which will be useful for making a more systematic search for developing better reagents for vanadium.

The excellent qualities of PBHA as a reagent for the detection and determination of vanadium (V)¹⁻³ provided an impetus for undertaking a systematic search for better reagents from the family of hydroxamic acids⁴. It is often possible to improve a reagent by varying the nature of substituent groups attached to its functional grouping. It was with this object in mind that a number of N-aryl hydroxamic acids, having different substituent groups attached to the carbon and nitrogen atoms of the hydroxamic acid functional grouping

were synthesised⁵⁻⁸. In this communication the reactions of these synthesised N-aryl hydroxamic acids with vanadium (V) in concentrated hydrochloric acid solutions are examined. The extraction behaviour of the vanadium (V) complexes, thus formed, is studied qualitatively. The absorption spectra of the chloroform extracts of the complexes are measured in the visible region for comparing the molar absorptivities at the respective wavelengths of maximum absorption.

As a result of this investigation it is found that among the 27 N-aryl hydroxamic acids examined here, N-phenyleinnamohydroxamic acid (abbreviated as PCHA) is the most sensitive reagent for the spectrophotometric determination of vanadium (V)⁹. The molar absorptivity of its bluish-violet complex is $6,300 \pm 50$ litre/mole cm. as compared to $4,600 \pm 50$

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litre/mole cm. for the violet complex of PBHA, both being calculated on the basis of vanadium and at their wavelengths of maximum absorption. Further, the PCHA reaction shows, improved selectivity for vanadium (V). It tolerates zirconium (IV) which otherwise interferes in the determination of vanadium (V) with PBHA.

EXPERIMENTAL

All the 27 N-aryl hydroxamic were synthesised and purified by recrystallization from benzene and petroleum ether (boiling range 60–80°)⁷. Their 0.1% w/v. (0.005 *M* approximately) solutions in ethyl-alcohol free chloroform were used for all extraction work. These solutions are stable for several days when stored in amber bottles.

All other chemicals and apparatus used were the same as described earlier⁴.

Colour Reaction : In general, the N-aryl hydroxamic acids reacted with vanadium (V) in a manner similar to that of PBHA described earlier². The complexes formed from concentrated hydrochloric acid solutions could be extracted by several organic solvents such as chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, *o*-dichloro-benzene, ethyl acetate, diethyl ether and benzene. Chloroform was found to be the most suitable extractant. It must, however, be free from ethyl-alcohol otherwise difficulties similar to those experienced with PBHA are encountered².

Procedure for Development of Colour : Transfer an aliquot of the oxidised solution, containing 0.02 to 0.2 mg. of vanadium (V), to a separatory funnel and add distilled water and hydrochloric acid until the volume is about 25 ml. and acidity between 2 and 10*M*. Add 10 ml. of 0.005*M* chloroform solution of the N-aryl hydroxamic acid and extract the colour in the organic phase by vigorous shaking. Allow the two layers to separate and collect the chloroform layer in a 50 ml. beaker containing about 1.5 g. of anhydrous sodium sulphate. Wash the aqueous layer two times with 5-ml. portions of chloroform to remove any residual colour, and add the washings to the contents of the beaker. Decant the coloured solution from the beaker to a 25 ml volumetric flask. Wash out the adhering colour from the sodium sulphate crystals with small portions of chloroform, combine the washings with the main solution, and dilute to the mark.

Absorption spectra : The spectra of the coloured chloroform extracts were determined using appropriate compensating blank solutions (chloroform being used for all colourless hydroxamic acids). It was observed that for a particular hydroxamic acid the wavelength of the maximum absorption of its coloured extract did not vary if the hydrochloric acid concentration of the aqueous phase was more than 2*M*.

In studies concerning the comparison of the molar absorptivities of the coloured extracts the hydrochloric acid concentration of the aqueous phase was adjusted to 4*M*. To ensure the quantitative extraction of vanadium the aqueous layer was repeatedly shaken with aliquots of reagent solution till it gave no colour. The applicability of Beer's law to coloured extracts was verified. The molar absorptivities of the coloured systems were calculated at the wavelengths of their maximum absorption and on the basis of vanadium content.

The results of this study are presented in Table I and the absorption spectra of a few typical coloured extracts are shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1.—Absorption spectra of vanadium(V) complexes (4.7 mg, vanadium/litre) from 4*N* hydrochloric acid with chloroform containing,
 (A) *N*-phenylcinnamohydroxamic acid,
 (B) *N*-phenyl-*p*-methoxybenzohydroxamic acid,
 (C) *N*-phenyl-*m*-methylbenzohydroxamic acid,
 (D) *N*-phenylbenzohydroxamic acid, and
 (E) *N*-phenyl-*n*-butyrohydroxamic acid.

Composition of Vanadium (V) Complexes : The composition of the vanadium (V) complexes formed in (i) strongly acidic, and (ii) weakly acidic solutions (*pH* 1 to 6) were determined by Job's method of continuous variations¹⁰, as modified by Vosburgh and Cooper¹¹ and applied to two-phase systems by Pierce and his co-workers^{12,13}.

Procedure : Transfer to a 100 ml. dry separatory funnel \times ml. of $1.829 \times 10^{-3} M$ solution of vanadium (V), $10 - X$ ml. of water, 5 ml. of concentrated hydrochloric acid (sp. gr. 1.18), $10 - X$ ml. of $1.829 \times 10^{-3} M$ solution of *N*-PCHA in ethyl alcohol-free chloroform and x ml. of chloroform. The total volumes of aqueous and organic phases were thus always 15 ml. and 10 ml., respectively. Shake the funnel vigorously for 5 min. and allow the phases to separate. Collect the chloroform layer in a 50 ml. beaker which contains about 1.5 g. of anhydrous sodium sulphate. Wash the aqueous phase two times with 5 ml. portions of chloroform to remove any residual colour. Decant the coloured solution from the beaker

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into a 25 ml. volumetric flask and wash out the adhering colour from the sodium sulphate crystals with small portions of chloroform. Mix the washings with the main solution and dilute to volume.

Measure the absorbance of the solutions at three wavelengths near the absorption band and plot the data between absorbance and mole-fraction of vanadium.

Similar studies were made at other concentrations and also with several other *N*-aryl hydroxamic acids. The *pH* of the aqueous phase, for studies made in weakly acidic media, was adjusted with caustic soda and hydrochloric acid and no buffer solutions were used. Representative Job's curves for PBHA and PCHA are shown in figure 2. In each of these

Figure 2.—Determination of ratio of vanadium(V) to hydroxamic acid by method of continuous variations (refer to text).

(A) Vanadium = PBHA = $1.829 \times 10^{-3} M$

(B) Vanadium = PCHA = $1.829 \times 10^{-3} M$

complexes the metal to ligand ratio was found to be two molecules of hydroxamic acid for one atom of vanadium. Similar conclusions were drawn by Ryan¹⁴ in his studies with PBHA and by Majumdar and Das¹⁵ in their studies with *N*-*o*-tolylbenzohydroxamic acid.

It is interesting that in each of the complexes studied in weakly acidic media (*pH* 1 to 6 approximately) the metal to ligand ratio was found to be two molecules of hydroxamic acid for one atom of vanadium.

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DISCUSSION

All the *N*-aryl hydroxamic acids react with vanadium (V) in concentrated hydrochloric acid solutions and form coloured complexes which are extracted in chloroform. However, the replacement of R₁ and R₂ by different substituent groups

brings about interesting changes in the vanadium (V) complexes of the modified hydroxamic acids. This is illustrated by the data presented in Table I on the vanadium (V) complexes obtained from concentrated hydrochloric acid solutions. The colours of the complexes vary from reddish-violet to bluish-violet, the 'position of absorption bands from 500 to 540 m μ and the molar absorptivities from 3,850 to 6,300 litre/mole cm.

TABLE I
Spectral Characteristics of Coloured Vanadium(V)-N-Aryl Hydroxamates in Chloroform (from ~4N HCl)

S.N.	Hydroxamic Acid	Colour of Chloroform Extract	Wavelength of Maximum Absorption m μ	Molar Absorptivity* ϵ
1	N-Phenylbenzo-	V	510	4,650
2	N- <i>p</i> -Tolyl- <i>o</i> -methylbenzo-	BV	530	4,750
3	N-Phenyl- <i>m</i> -methylbenzo-	BV	530	5,150
4	N- <i>p</i> -Tolyl- <i>m</i> -methylbenzo-	BV	535	5,250
5	N- <i>p</i> -Tolyl- <i>p</i> -methylbenzo-	V	530	4,900
6	N-Phenyl- <i>p</i> -fluorobenzo-	V	525	4,400
7	N- <i>p</i> -Tolyl- <i>p</i> -fluorobenzo-	V	530	4,500
8	N- <i>p</i> -Tolyl- <i>o</i> -chlorobenzo-	BV	530	4,500
9	N-Phenyl- <i>o</i> -bromobenzo-	BV	530	4,450
10	N- <i>p</i> -Tolyl- <i>o</i> -bromobenzo-	BV	535	4,500
11	N- <i>p</i> -Tolyl- <i>m</i> -bromobenzo-	V	530	4,450
12	N-Phenyl- <i>p</i> -bromobenzo-	V	525	4,550
13	N- <i>p</i> -Tolyl- <i>p</i> -bromobenzo-	V	530	4,650
14	N- <i>p</i> -Tolyl- <i>o</i> -iodobenzo-	BV	535	4,400
15	N-Phenyl- <i>p</i> -methoxybenzo-	BV	535	5,900
16	N- <i>p</i> -Tolyl- <i>p</i> -methoxybenzo-	BV	540	6,100
17	N-Phenylcinnamo-	BV	540	6,300
18	N-Phenylphenylaceto-	RV	500	4,400
19	N- <i>p</i> -Tolylphenylaceto-	RV	505	4,500
20	N-Phenylphenoxyaceto-	RV	500	3,850
21	N-Phenyl- <i>p</i> -chlorophenoxyaceto-	RV	500	3,850
22	N-Phenyl- <i>n</i> -butyro-	RV	500	4,400
23	N- <i>p</i> -Tolyl- <i>n</i> -butyro-	RV	505	4,500
24	N-Phenyllauro-	RV	500	4,400
25	N- <i>p</i> -Tolyllauro-	RV	505	4,500
26	N-Phenylpalmito-	RV	500	4,400
27	N- <i>p</i> -Tolylpalmito-	RV	505	4,500

V = Violet; BV = Bluish Violet; RV = Reddish Violet.

* The average of at least 12 measurements of 4 samples of different vanadium concentrations.

Replacement of phenyl group attached to the carbon atom of the hydroxamic acid functional grouping by an aliphatic chain causes slight hypochromic and hypsochromic effect. The colours of the complexes also change to reddish-violet. This is illustrated by the vanadium (V) complexes of hydroxamic acids derived from *n*-butyric, lauric and palmitic acids. It is observed that the length of the saturated aliphatic chain has little influence on the position and intensity of the absorption bands of vanadium (V) complexes. This is true even for the complexes of hydroxamic acids derived from phenylacetic acid, in which one $-\text{CH}_2-$ group separates the carbonyl and phenyl groups.

In the vanadium (V) complexes of *N*-phenylphenoxyaceto- and *N*-*p*-chlorophenoxyaceto-hydroxamic acids the hypochromic effect is still more prominent. These acids are unsuitable as extractive reagents for vanadium (V) because with them the full colour develops slowly and on repeated extraction. Halogen substituted hydroxamic acids too are unsuitable as extractive reagents on similar grounds.

Replacement of the phenyl group attached to the C or N atoms by the *p*-tolyl group causes a slight, though definite, bathochromic and hyperchromic effect on the absorption bands of vanadium (V) complexes. A similar effect is more prominently reflected in the vanadium (V) complexes of methoxy substituted hydroxamic acids.

Conclusions on the influence of position of substituent groups can be drawn if a sufficiently large number of *N*-aryl hydroxamic acids are studied.

The increase in the length of conjugation by the introduction of side chain double bond, $-\text{CH}=\text{CH}-$, between the carbon atom of carbonyl group and phenyl group (in PCHA) causes a conspicuous increase in the molar absorptivity of the vanadium (V) complex. The colour of the complex changes to bluish-violet and the absorption band registers a bathochromic shift.

On the basis of above and previous⁴ studies it is felt that by further increasing the length of conjugation by introducing larger number of side chain double bonds in the group for R_2 , it should be possible to develop more sensitive reagents for vanadium (V). Further, it will be worthwhile investigating the influence of other substituent groups.

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